

Studies on the Preparation and Characterization of Monochlorodithiocarbamato Complexes of Di-*n*-Butyl- and Di-*n*-Hexyltin(IV)

C. P. SHARMA, N. KUMAR and S. CHANDRA

National Physical Laboratory, New Delhi-110 012

and

B. S. GARG

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

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Dialkyltin(IV) monochlorodithiocarbamato complexes of the type $R_2Sn(IV)-[R'R''dtc]Cl$ or $R_2Sn(IV)[morph.dtc]Cl$ ($R=n-Bu, n-Hex, R'=R''=Me, Et, i-Pr$; $R'=Me$ and $R''=Ph$) have been prepared by the reaction of di-*n*-butyl- or di-*n*-hexyltin(IV) dichloride with the sodium salt of respective dithiocarbamic acid in 1 : 1 molar ratio in dry acetone. The ir, 1H nmr and Mossbauer studies indicate an anisobidentate character for the dtc (dithiocarbamate) ligand in these complexes.

UNLIKE metal dithiocarbamates¹⁻⁵, a study of organotin(IV)⁶ and tin(IV) N,N-disubstituted dithiocarbamates⁷⁻¹⁰ reveals that the dithiocarbamate group can act as monodentate (a), bidentate or chelating (b, c) or anisobidentate (d), ligand. In

the study of organotin(IV) N,N-dithiocarbamates, techniques such as infrared^{1,3-5}, 1H nmr⁵⁻⁹, Mossbauer¹⁰⁻¹⁵ and X-ray diffraction¹⁶⁻¹⁸ have been used to assign structure.

The present communication reports the synthesis and characterization of some new diorganotin(IV) monochloro dithiocarbamates of the type $R_2Sn(IV)-[R'R''dtc]Cl$ or $R_2Sn(IV)[morph.dtc]Cl$ ($R=n-Bu, n-Hex, R'=R''=Me, Et, i-Pr$; $R'=Me$ and $R''=Ph$), which have been characterized on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral data (ir, 1H nmr and Mossbauer) and the "anisobidentate" nature of the dtc moiety has been established.

Experimental

Synthesis of the intermediate compounds :

i. Sodium salts of the N,N-dialkyl dithiocarbamate ligands (where alkyl group is methyl-, ethyl-, isopropyl, morpholine and N-methyl and N-phenyl) were prepared by the reaction of equimolecular amounts of the respective secondary amine, carbon-disulphide and sodium hydroxide in aqueous medium at 10-15°¹⁹

ii. Di-*n*-butyl- and di-*n*-hexyltin(IV) dichlorides were prepared by the disproportionation reaction of tetra-*n*-butyl- and tetra-*n*-hexyltin(IV) with tin tetrachloride²⁰⁻²¹.

Synthesis of di-*n*-butyl- and di-*n*-hexyltin(IV) monochloro-N,N-disubstituted dithiocarbamate :

Di-n-butyltin(IV) monochloro-N,N-dimethyl dithiocarbamate: To a solution of di-*n*-butyltin dichloride (3.03 g ; 0.01 mol) in dry acetone (75 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring a solution of sodium salt of N,N-dimethyldithiocarbamate (1.43 g ; 0.01 mol) in dry acetone (50 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 2 hr and filtered. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure to get a viscous liquid which upon distillation under reduced pressure gave the final product, a colourless viscous liquid in 60% yield.

Similarly, the complexes of di-*n*-butyl- and di-*n*-hexyltin(IV) with monochloro-N,N-diethyl-, N,N-isopropyl-, morpholine-, and N-methyl phenyl dithiocarbamate were prepared.

Infrared spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 621 grating spectrometer using KBr pressed disks for solid compounds and thin films for liquids, in the region 4000-250 cm^{-1} . Proton magnetic resonance spectra were recorded at ambient temperature (28°) at sweep width of 500 Hz with a Varian A-60 spectrometer. Spectra were recorded in triplicate and the values given in Table 3 are average values ; the magnetic field sweep was calibrated with a standard sample of chloroform and tetramethylsilane (1%) in deuterated chloroform.

Mossbauer experiments were performed at liquid air temperature employing a standard cons-

tant acceleration spectrometer based on electro-mechanical feedback system as described in literature²². The data was stored in a 1024 channels ND-100 multichannel analyser used in a multichannel scaling mode. The resultant spectra were fitted using a computer programme which assumes the Lorentzian line shape and treats line position, intensity and half width as independent parameters in a multiple iteration least squares fitting procedures using IBM 360/44 computer. The source used was 5 mCi ¹¹⁹Sn in calcium stannate matrix. The spectrometer was calibrated using four inner lines of the magnetic hyperfine spectrum of ⁵⁷Fe in standard reference iron foil. All the isomer shifts are referred to CaSnO₃ at room temperature and are compared directly with the room temperature isomer shifts of gray tin. Samples of tin complexes were made by injecting the liquid into a hermetically sealed absorber cell made up of copper disc and mylar sheets and mounting it on a copper sample holder which could be attached directly to the copper cold finger of a liquid air dewar. The temperature of the samples was measured by a copper constantan thermocouple with an accuracy of ± 0.5 K.

Quantitative estimation of carbon and hydrogen was done by using microanalytical apparatus; nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method, tin and sulphur were estimated gravimetrically as SnO₂ and barium sulphate (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

Organotin dithiocarbamates of the type R₂Sn(IV)-Cl[S₂CNR'₂] (R = *n*-Bu, *n*-Hex, R' = Me, Et, *i*-Pr, or R'₂ = morpholine and methyl phenyl) have been prepared in good yields by the reaction of diorganotin dichloride and anhydrous sodium salt of the respective dithiocarbamic acid in acetone according to the following equation :

All the monochloro dithiocarbamate complexes of di-*n*-butyl and di-*n*-hexyltin are colourless viscous liquids. These complexes are soluble in benzene, chloroform, acetone, alcohol and are quite stable at room temperature in dry and inert atmosphere.

Infrared spectra : The analyses of the ir spectra of di-*n*-butyl-, and di-*n*-hexyltin(IV) monochloro dithiocarbamates (Table 2) indicate an anisobidentate 'unsymmetrical' character of the dtc ligands in these complexes because of the following.

i. There is only one absorption band due to $\nu(C=N)$ at ~ 1500 cm⁻¹ and a broad band due to $\nu(C=S)$ at ~ 1000 cm⁻¹. An explanation of this broad band may be that both the sulphur atoms of the dtc group participate in bonding with the tin metal atom but there is a slight difference in the Sn-S bond lengths, resulting in a corresponding difference in C-S bond lengths for both the sulphur

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF MONOCHLORO DITHIOCARBAMATO COMPLEXES OF di-*n*-BUTYL AND di-*n*-HEXYLTIN(IV)

Compound	Physical state b.p. °C	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)					
		C	H	S	N	Sn	Cl
1. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl	Liquid 136-6 1 mm	34.20 (34.00)	5.85 (6.18)	16.23 (16.48)	3.30 (3.60)	30.01 (30.57)	9.52 (9.14)
2. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)ethyl	Liquid 120-1 0.5 mm	37.05 (37.48)	6.23 (6.72)	16.65 (15.37)	3.60 (3.36)	28.90 (28.51)	8.98 (8.52)
3. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc) <i>i</i> -propyl	Liquid 142-8 2 mm	39.81 (40.52)	7.00 (7.20)	14.75 (14.40)	3.60 (3.15)	17.02 (26.72)	8.82 (7.99)
4. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)morph	Liquid 138-9 1 mm	35.85 (36.26)	5.65 (6.04)	15.21 (14.87)	3.60 (3.25)	27.01 (27.59)	7.82 (8.25)
5. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl, phenyl	Liquid 151-2 2 mm	42.70 (42.64)	6.10 (5.77)	14.60 (14.21)	2.85 (3.10)	25.94 (26.35)	8.23 (7.88)
6. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl	Liquid 139-40 1 mm	40.13 (40.52)	7.50 (7.20)	14.17 (14.40)	3.50 (3.15)	27.12 (26.72)	7.63 (7.99)
7. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)ethyl	Liquid 134-5 0.8 mm	43.70 (43.20)	7.40 (7.62)	13.25 (13.55)	3.25 (2.96)	24.87 (25.13)	7.28 (7.51)
8. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc) <i>i</i> -propyl	Liquid 120-1 0.5 mm	45.23 (45.58)	8.80 (7.99)	13.16 (12.79)	3.01 (2.79)	24.01 (23.73)	6.73 (7.09)
9. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)morph	Liquid 129-30 0.5 mm	42.20 (41.95)	7.40 (6.99)	12.83 (13.16)	3.07 (2.87)	24.19 (24.14)	3.50 (3.29)
10. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl, phenyl	Liquid 136-7 1 mm	47.62 (47.41)	6.99 (6.71)	12.27 (12.64)	2.43 (2.76)	23.16 (23.44)	7.30 (7.01)

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT INFRARED DATA OF THE MONOCHLORO DITHIOCARBAMATO COMPLEXES OF di-*n*-BUTYL- AND di-*n*-HEXYLTIN(IV)

Compound	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{O})$
1. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl	1480 s	975 s	380 m 370 w	580 m 555 s
2. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)ethyl	1500 s	990 m	380 m 365 w	590 m 550 s
3. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc) <i>i</i> -propyl	1490 s	960 m	390 m 385 w	595 m 560 s
4. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)morph	1490 s	1000 m	380 m 370 w	580 m 560 s
5. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl,phenyl	1490 s	1000 s	400 m 385 w	590 m 555 m
6. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl	1465 m	980 s	380 w 375 w	580 w 555 s
7. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)ethyl	1500 s	995 s	380 m 375 w	585 m 555 m
8. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc) <i>i</i> -propyl	1490 s	950 m	390 m 365 w	595 w 560 w
9. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)morph	1490 s	1005 m	390 m 380 w	510 s 540 s
10. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl,phenyl	1484 m	1000 s	390 w 370 w	585 s 560 m

s=strong, m=medium, w=weak.

TABLE 3—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF MONOCHLORO DITHIOCARBAMATO COMPLEXES OF di-*n*-BUTYL- AND di-*n*-HEXYLTIN(IV)

Compound	Resonance signals due to Sn-Bu/Sn-hex protons (τ ppm)	Proton signals due to NR ₂ protons (τ ppm)			
		-CH ₃	-OH ₂	-OH	O ₂ H ₂
1. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl	8.10-9.00 m	6.50 s	—	—	—
2. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)ethyl	8.14-8.95 m	8.65 t	6.15 q	—	—
3. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc) <i>i</i> -propyl	8.14-9.05 m	8.50 d	—	5.35 m	—
4. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)morph	8.12-9.08 m	—	6.12 d 5.90 d	—	—
5. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl,phenyl	8.10-9.01 m	6.20 s	—	—	2.38 s
6. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl	8.12-9.08 m	6.50 s	—	—	—
7. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)ethyl	8.15-9.08 m	8.65 t	6.13 q	—	—
8. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc) <i>i</i> -propyl	8.30-9.10 m	8.50 d	—	5.35 m	—
9. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)morph	8.10-9.20 m	—	6.20 d 5.94 d	—	—
10. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl,phenyl	8.12-9.10 m	6.30 s	—	—	2.50 s

Spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ solution

s=strong, d=doublet, m=multiplet, q=quatret.

atoms. The difference may, however, be too small to resolve the band into two peaks.

ii. In the far ir region, two absorption bands are present at $\sim 400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ thus indicating two (M-S) stretching.

iii. A ligand vibration mode at $\sim 900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is present in all these complexes.

iv. Presence of two bands at ~ 580 and $\sim 560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes are assigned to Sn-C (asym) and Sn-C (sym) stretching modes, respectively and suggest that C-Sn-C moiety is not linear. Thus the molecule deviates from the *trans* geometry.

The room temperature nmr studies on various monochloro dithiocarbamate complexes of di-*n*-butyl- and di-*n*-hexyltin(IV) are reported in Table 3. The proton magnetic resonance absorption of the complexes show two types of signals, i.e., due to Sn-Bu or Sn-Hex, and NR₂ protons.

¹H NMR spectra: ¹H NMR spectra of these complexes show that the N-bonded R groups are equivalent in these complexes because of the following. There appears only one singlet at $\sim 6.4 \tau$ due to N-Me protons in *n*-Bu₂SnCl[S₂CNMe₂] and *n*-Hex₂SnCl[S₂CNMe₂] complexes. In the analogous ethyl dithiocarbamate complexes only one type of quartet at $\sim 6.1 \tau$ due to N-methylene protons and a triplet at $\sim 8.6 \tau$ due to methyl protons of ethyl group of the dithiocarbamate moiety are present. In isopropyl dtc complexes, a heptet at

$\sim 5.3 \tau$ due to N-C-H protons and a doublet at

$\sim 8.5 \tau$ due to methyl protons are present. In the N-methyl, N-phenyl dtc complexes only one type of proton signal at $\sim 6.3 \tau$ (due to N-methyl protons) and the other at $\sim 2.5 \tau$ (due to N-phenyl) are present. The proton signals of the morpholine

group, i.e., at ~ 5.9 (O-CH₂) and ~ 6.2 τ (N-CH₂) protons again confirm the equivalence of the R₂ group in these complexes.

The equivalence of the R' group of the dtc moiety illustrates that these complexes are stereochemically non-rigid at least at ambient temperature. Further, the position of the proton signals due to methylene protons of the ethyl complexes suggest that the mode of bonding of dithiocarbamate moiety is anisobidentate. As expected, the methylene protons of the ligand ethyl group are more sensitive to variations in the nature of the metal-ligand bond than are the methyl protons of the ligand. The chemical shift of CH₂ proton lies intermediate between the value observed for the sodium salt of the ligand at 5.87 τ (in which the C=S bond is preserved and the ligand act as monodentate entity) and that observed for the nickel(II) complex at 6.41 τ (in which the ligand is acting as a symmetrical bidentate moiety with two essentially equal metal-sulphur interactions). It should, however, be noted that these data refer to solution (rather than neat solid) species and that little is known about the integrity of the compound when neat solid and solution species are involved.

PROTON MAGNETIC RESONANCE DATA

	Na(Et ₂ dtc)	R ₂ SnCl(Et ₂ dtc)	Ni(Et ₂ dtc) ₂
CH ₃	8.8	8.65	8.81
CH ₂	5.87	6.15	6.41

Proton shifts are given in τ ppm

Mossbauer spectra: The spectra of the dialkyltin monochloro dithiocarbamates (Table 4) consist of well resolved doublets indicating a lack of cubic symmetry of the charge distribution around the metal atom in these complexes.

TABLE 4—MOSSBAUER SPECTRAL DATA OF MONOCHLORO DITHIOCARBAMATO COMPLEXES OF di-*n*-BUTYL- AND di-*n*-HEXYLTIN(IV)

Compound	I.S.	Q.S.
	mm/sec	mm/sec
1. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl	1.42	3.05
2. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc)ethyl	1.53	2.89
3. <i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(dtc) <i>i</i> -propyl	1.59	2.81
4. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)methyl	1.43	2.91
5. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)ethyl	1.52	2.96
6. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc) <i>iso</i> -propyl	1.40	3.05
7. <i>n</i> -Hex ₂ SnCl(dtc)morph	1.47	3.09

The Mossbauer measurements were carried out at 88 K. All the isomer shifts are with respect of CaSnO₃ absorber at room temp.

The quadrupole splitting, isomer shifts are corrected within ± 0.05 mm/sec.

All the complexes reported here can exist in two possible isomers, *cis* and *trans*. From the extensive data available²³⁻²⁵, it is seen that for octahedral *trans* dialkyltin(IV) complexes having axial symmetry such as (CH₃)₂SnF₂, (CH₃)₂Sn(NCS)₂, (CH₃)₂Sn(acac)₂, for which the configurational assignment is based on unambiguous X-ray diffraction data, the

observed quadrupole splitting lies in the range $3.5 < \frac{1}{2} e^2 qQ < 4.6$ mm/sec. On the other hand the corresponding *cis* compounds result in resonance spectra for which $1.5 < \frac{1}{2} e^2 qQ < 2.2$ mm/sec is in agreement with the predictions of the point charge model which show that Q.S. (*trans*) = 2 Q.S. (*cis*). The observed quadrupole splittings for the di-*n*-butyl, and di-*n*-hexyltin(IV) monochloro dithiocarbamate complexes are smaller than those observed for axially symmetric *trans* octahedral complexes of the type R₂SnX₄ and larger than those observed for the analogous *cis* configurations. The other geometry which suggests itself is that of distorted tetrahedral configuration in which the two dtc ligands acts as unidentate moieties with a single tin-sulphur σ -bond, having the second sulphur atom in each ligand in a non-bonding orientation. Such a structure can, however, be ruled out on the basis of the data²⁶ on dialkyltin(IV) *bis*-thiols. The observed quadrupole splittings for (CH₃)₂Sn(SCH₂C₆H₅)₂, (CH₃)₂Sn(SC_{1,5}H_{2,5})₂ and (C₄H₉)₂Sn(SC_{1,5}H_{2,5})₂ are 1.65, 1.59 and 1.58 mm/sec, respectively at 80 K and it is concluded that this magnitude of Q.S. parameter is properly associated with a distorted tetrahedral structure for dialkyltin compounds having two tin-sulphur σ -bonds. The present data can be understood in terms of two different tin-sulphur interactions per ligand, one of which is a normal tin-sulphur bond while the other is with a considerably weaker bonding interaction between the metal and the ligand, described by Herber^{15a} as "anisobidentate".

On the basis of above discussion of ir, ¹H nmr and Mossbauer data, it can be suggested that in these monochloro dithiocarbamate complexes of di-*n*-butyl-, and di-*n*-hexyltin(IV), both the sulphur atoms of the dtc group participate in the bonding with different Sn-S interactions (anisobidentate or unsymmetric bonding character).

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